

Socio-Economic Change in the Jain Community of Bundelkhand

Prof. Prakash C. Jain*

This article summarises economic, educational, socio-cultural and religious changes in the Jain community of Bundelkhand that occurred within a span of two-three generations. As detailed in the methodological section below, it is based on a larger sociological study on the same theme. How, why and to what extent these changes have affected the contemporary Jain community of Bundelkhand is the focus of this study. In order to do that the data obtained through a survey in the region are “compared” to two sets of past/historical referents: (i) Autobiography “*Meri Jeevan Gatha*” (*My Life Saga*) of Kshullak Ganesh Prasad Varni (1874-1961) which was written some time during the mid-1940s and first published in 1949. It details in narrative style the socio-economic and educational condition of the Bundelkhand Jain community of the late 19th and the first half of the 20th centuries; and (ii) author’s lived experiences and observations as an adolescent and later on as a sociologist who was born and brought up in Saidpur village of the then Jhansi district, and subsequently studied for matriculation examination at Shri Varni Jain Inter College, Lalitpur during 1960-62. Since then although the author has been living outside the Bundelkhand region, scores of visits had been made during the past half a century to the various parts of the

region in order to meet family members, relatives and friends, and attend marriage and death ceremonies, etc.

- Bundelkhand is a culturally-homogeneous sub-region in central India. Officially it consists of seven districts of Uttar Pradesh and six districts of Madhya Pradesh. However the greater or cultural Bundelkhand extends to more than two dozen districts, mostly in Madhya Pradesh. Economically the region is highly dependent on agriculture and mining with very little development in educational, industrial and infrastructural sectors. Consequently, the region is characterised by high level of poverty and out-migration. With about 20 million population (18.5 million in 2011), the social composition of Bundelkhand is dominated by OBC and SC & ST communities. The level of urbanisation is relatively low and other demographic indicators about status of women, child mortality rate, education and healthcare facilities, etc. are not very encouraging. Bundelkhand has been home to Digambar Jainism since about the 4th century AD. The successive ruling dynasties of the region such as Maurya, Gupta, Pratihara, Parmar, Kachchhap, Kalchuri, Chandela and Bundela had given royal patronage in varying degrees and at different points of time to Jainism with the result that the Jain community has been flourishing in Bundelkhand ever since, and continues to do so even today. The Jains have been vitally integrated into the economic structure and socio-cultural life of the region. The great temples built by them at Khajuraho, Devgarh, Gwalior, Chanderi, Nainagiri and a large number of other places are eloquent testimony to the prosperity of the Jain community in the region. And this has been so in spite of the fact that in modern times they have always constituted a miniscule community in Bundelkhand. In 2011 census

* Formerly Professor of Sociology, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.

their population was enumerated at 148,612 persons, that is, about 0.8% of the region's total population.

Historically, Jains have constituted a unique economic niche for themselves in the Bundelkhand region which has been underdeveloped since the British colonial days. Uncertain climatic conditions, frequent famines, lack of irrigation facilities, unegalitarian social structure, increasing population pressure on agricultural land have further added to the economic woes of Bundelkhand. Not surprisingly, until about a couple of generations ago the Jain community of Bundelkhand also suffered from some of these socio-economic characteristics of the region. Compared to the Jains of other parts of the country, a majority of Jains of Bundelkhand were relatively less affluent and progressive. The vast majority of them were involved in small-time trading and commercial activities. Their socio-religious attitude was characterised by conservatism and religious orthodoxy. However during the past couple of decades this over-all situation of the community has been changing for the better. The Jains of the region have been showing significant amount of predisposition to social change and modernisation, particularly in regard to education and occupational aspects. And this was precisely the focus of this study. Before we summarize our findings of the study, a brief account of research methodology would be in order.

Research Methodology

The study was designed as an exploratory sociological study as there are very few such studies on the Jain community in India. Data for the study were collected during February and March 2014 through a questionnaire in the four core districts of Bundelkhand, namely Lalitpur, Jhansi, Sagar and Tikamgarh. The first two of them are located in U.P.-Bundelkhand

and last two in M.P.-Bundelkhand. Data were collected not only from the above mentioned four cities, but also from two tehsil (sub-district) towns (Mahroni and Madawara) and three villages (Saidpur, Sadumal and Birdha – all of them located in Lalitpur district). Additionally, the data were also collected from about twenty Bundelkhandi Jain respondents who have been living in different towns and cities of India outside the region. These places include Delhi, Jaipur, Varanasi, Nagpur, Pune, Bhopal, Indore, Ratlam, Badot, Morena, Shivpuri, etc. In all, 210 questionnaires were sent by mail/personally distributed to the respondents, of which 180 were found to be in order.

As per our survey, the overwhelming majority of respondents were male (96.1%), married (95.0%), Terapanthi Digambar Jains belonging to mainly *Parwar* (70%), and *Golapurv* (20%) castes. The rural-urban break-up of respondents was 31% and 69% respectively. A majority of respondents were highly educated with 23% of them having studied at Jain Sanskrit *vidyalayas*. Employment-wise 55% were employed in various kinds of services while the rest were engaged in family business and other activities. The income distribution was as follows: about 49% were earning Rs. 5 Lakhs or less, 28% between Rs. 5-10 lakhs, 11% between Rs. 10-15 lakhs and the rest were earning more than Rs. 15 lakhs – a few of them earning even Crores of Rupees.

Demographic Changes

As per 2011 census the total population of Jains in Bundelkhand was 148.612 which is about 3.5% of the total Jain population in India. Of these 52% were male and 48% female. The level of urbanisation is 66% which is significantly lower than the Jain national average of 80%. The Jain sex ratio in Bundelkhand is 917 which is lower than the Jain national figure of 954 females per 1000 males. Data from our study also suggest the small size family norm of 4-5 members. Age of marriage also appears

to have gone up by a few years in recent decades. Our field work data also suggest a considerable number of boys beyond marriageable age remaining unmarried, particularly in villages and towns due to skewed sex ratio and other sociological factors. Among other demographic changes literacy (94.18%) and education among the Jains of Bundelkhand have certainly gone up which is reflected in increased number of them working/getting employed as professionals in public as well as private sectors within the region and outside it.

There appears to be a fair amount of out-migration of Jains, particularly of highly educated professionals from Bundelkhand as many of them happen to be getting education outside the region and thereby easily getting suitable jobs there itself. Even if they are willing to come back to their native places, the region is not developed enough to provide them suitable employment. A number of Bundelkhandi Jains have also settled abroad, particularly in North America.

Economic and Educational Changes

In the economy of Bundelkhand Jains are more or less exclusively associated with whole sale as well as retail trade for centuries. While they still continue to dominate these sectors, newer economic and occupational opportunities have also been opened up for them during the past few decades. To begin with, trade and commercial activities have expanded to include newer products and services related to construction and housing, mechanisation of agriculture, irrigation, information technology, processed and fast food, etc. Thus quite a number of Jains have shifted to wholesale and retail sale of hardware, water pumps, tractor parts, photocopiers, mobiles, TV sets, ACs, washing machines, motor cycles parts and so on. In the textile sector readymade garments have emerged as major items of trade in both rural and urban areas. Thus trading activities have gone beyond supplying only household and provision goods, and in the

Bundelkhand region the Jains appear to have taken full advantage of this transformation.

Besides expanding and consolidating their class position as traders, some of the Jains have moved to entrepreneurship in areas like flour, rice and dal mills, saw mills, manufacturing of readymade garments and school uniforms, operation of petrol pumps, buses and trucks, etc. A few of them have also gone into taking up contracts for construction of bridges, roads and housing colonies.

Crystallisation and consolidation as a class segment of highly educated professionals is another development that has taken place among the Jains of Bundelkhand during the past three-four decades. Earlier, this class segment was confined to only male school and college teachers, village land record-keepers (*lekhpāls*), middle-ranked government servants, and a minuscule number of engineers, doctors and lawyers. Today however, it has not only expanded multi-fold but also includes university professors, information technology personnel, business management and banking professionals, etc. As already mentioned, about 55% of our respondents were working as professionals and in service sector. During the past one hundred years or so the role of Jain Sanskrit *vidyālayas* in raising three or four generations of traditional Jain scholars (*Paṇḍits*) and in contributing towards the growth of college and university teachers of Jain Philosophy and Religion, Indology, Sanskrit, Pali, Prakrit and Hindi languages has been remarkably significant.

Income levels of Jains in Bundelkhand have gone up during the past couple of decades. This is clearly reflected in better living standards, increased use of home appliances and consumer goods such as refrigerators, cooking gas cylinders, washing machines, motor cycles, etc., better diet and better housing facilities in rural as well as urban areas. A vast majority of Jains in

Bundelkhand now have their own *pucca* houses equipped with in-house toilet facilities.

Social Structural Changes

The changes in economic and occupational structures logically takes us to consider the social and economic stratification systems in the Jain community of Bundelkhand. Although social stratification within the community continues to remain more or less intact as a three-tier hierarchical system consisting of *dhanikvarga* (affluent class), *tyāgivargā* (class of renouncers) and *janasadhāranā* (ordinary people), the economic stratification of the community is increasingly acquiring the form of a modern class system. This is obviously based on modern education, occupations, income/wealth and the attendant life style and the patterns of consumption. In the process the traditional hierarchy of Shrimant Seth, Seth, Singhai, etc. no longer correspond with the emerging economic stratification system and therefore losing its relevance. The community has never been economically homogeneous; it has been quite stratified and continues to be so in spite of undergoing modernisation and social change, and becoming relatively affluent by local Bundelkhand standards.

In spite of practising a distinct religion for centuries Jain community has so much affinity with the wider Hindu society that the Jains are often considered as upper caste Hindus. Until about a century ago a large majority of Jains themselves believed in this. This self-perception began to change with the activities of Shri Bharatvarshiya Digambar Jain Mahasabha (1895) and other regional and caste associations established during early decades of the 20th century. Since then the change was further strengthened over the decades by the consistent efforts of the Jain community leaders, *Paṇḍits*, ethnic press as well as *munis* and *tyāgis* with the result that today a great majority of Jains consider themselves as distinct and separate religious minority – something which the British Indian

government had recognised by enumerating the Jains as a distinct religious minority since the 1881 census, and which the Government of India confirmed by eventually granting them the minority status in January 2014. Although the Jains being a relatively affluent community do not require economic benefits or reservations in government jobs, the minority status accorded to them would certainly go a long way in protecting the Jain cultural heritage.

Increased education, occupational mobility and associated out-migration of Jains from Bundelkhand have deeply affected their key social structural institutions such as family, kinship and marriage, caste and class. In Bundelkhand, as in other parts of India, not only the kinship system has weakened, the structure and functions of family have also undergone changes which can be summarised as follows: small size, assertion of individuality in regard to choice of education and career and choice of marriage partner, democratisation of family relations, decrease in discrimination against girl child, etc. An ever increasing number of Jains have begun to realize that daughters are more dependable and reliable than sons, particularly in times of healthcare emergency. Even otherwise, unlike their Hindu counterparts, the Jains were not required to have a son for any religious or spiritual purpose.

Of all the social institutions, perhaps the marriage has undergone the most changes in the Jain community of Bundelkhand. To begin with, “poisonous” or “bad” marriages (*viṣavivāha*) in the form of child marriage, polygamy and age-incompatible marriages that were prevalent until about the middle of the 20th century have almost disappeared. Among other changes mention must be made of significant increase in the number of inter-religion and inter-caste marriages, acceptance of widow and divorcee remarriages and decrease in dowry demand. The duration of marriage ceremonies has been reduced from three-four days to about 24 hours or even less

over a period of about two generations. An increasing number of marriages are now solemnised by Jain *pandits*, and often during day time.

The system of arranged marriage has also undergone changes. Instead of marriage being arranged on one-to-one basis by family friends or relatives, most marriages today are arranged either through newspaper advertisements or increasingly by professional marriage agencies or marriage bureaus. Perhaps more radical change has occurred in regard to the customary bride groom's party going to bride's place for the marriage to get solemnised. In most cases this is no longer so; instead marriage now takes place at a mutually-agreed-upon place which often happens to be the groom's town or city. Depending on the mutual negotiations, the financial implications of this arrangement for both the parties vary accordingly. In most marriages expenditure on decoration and food has gone up many-folds in recent decades. In the process the specificity of Bundelkhandi style of Jain marriage has given way to Indian "filmi" style of marriage with the accompanying dance, music and multi-cuisine food, etc.

The social status of Jain women has undergone significant changes over the decades. Only two generations ago a large majority of women were either illiterate or were poorly educated. There was no question of their employment. Patriarchy as a social order prevailed and girls were routinely discriminated against in the Jain community; some of them were also subjected to "bad" marriages. Fortunately, all of this has now significantly changed for the better. Today Jain women are relatively free to have their say in the family, and to have choice in education, vocation and marriage. Not surprisingly, most Jain women have emerged as individuals capable of performing roles befitting a modern society. The problematic aspects of Jain women's life in Bundelkhand include skewed sex ratio (917 females per 1,000 males), lower work participation (about 11%), and practically

non-existent political participation, except voting exercise during national, regional or local elections. Notwithstanding the increased use of kitchen appliances and other gadgets, their share in the burden of household chores has also not lessened significantly.

Jain Way of Life

Most Jains of Bundelkhand are the followers of *Terāpanthi* Digambar Jainism which is more conservative than its *Biṣapanthi* counterpart. In spite of challenges to Terapanth orthodoxy by the emergent Kanjii panthic ideology, religious orthodoxy continues to prevail in the Jain community of Bundelkhand. Complete devotion to Jindeva, scriptures and ascetics is the hall mark of this orthodoxy. Not surprisingly, almost all the respondents (97%) believe that Jainism is the best of all religions. With the spread of education neo-orthodoxy is also gaining ground among the new generation of scholars and lay Jains who often interpret Jainism as a scientific religion. Thus as per our sample, about 84% of the followers of Jainism are orthodox/neo-orthodox; only about 15% of them can be considered as heterodox – simultaneously having faith in mainly Hindu gods and goddesses and/or worshiping family deities.

Our study suggests both continuity and change in various aspects of the Jain way of life in the region. One aspect of Jain way of life that has shown remarkable stability and continuity over perhaps the centuries is the routine of daily life (*dincharya*). This involves morning and early night visits to a Jain temple, meditation, contemplation and/or self-study of scriptures while inside the temple, use of cloth-strained water for drinking and cooking and taking dinner before sunset. These practices are widespread in the region. So much so that this daily routine is considered the very identity of a Jain. A daily visit to temple even for a few minutes is a must for Jains in the region; only in exceptional circumstances such as sickness it is avoided.

Celebrating Jain festivals, observing fast on auspicious occasions and visiting pilgrimage places are important indicators of Jain religiosity and the way of life. Thus almost all the Jains in Bundelkhand celebrate the 10-day Paryushanparva and a vast majority of them varyingly keep fast on this occasion. Again, almost all the Jains of Bundelkhand pay visits to both local/regional and national pilgrimage places. Every individual Jain aspires to visit some of the national pilgrimage centres like Sammedshikharji, Mahavirji and Girnarji at least once in their life-time.

Last but not the least, diet and dietary regulations on the day-to-day basis are very strictly observed by Jains of Bundelkhand. Apart from all non-vegetarian items including eggs, a number of vegetables such as garlic, onion, potato, *arvi*, brinjal, etc. are also not eaten by most of them. The overwhelming majority of Jains are not only teetotalers, they also do not consume any kinds of intoxicants. Honey is also avoided by many. Most Jain families in the region avoid taking food in market place, hotels and restaurants; instead they prefer to prepare most food items at home for reasons of purity, cleanliness and cloth-strained water.

Typical of a generational gap, the elders of the Jain community of Bundelkhand do not consider the younger generation as much religious and even socially responsible as they would have liked. A majority of our respondents echo this viewpoint and agree with the idea that the younger generation is generally indifferent towards religion which is reflected in their daily routine, food habits, attitude towards ascetics, etc. Reportedly, a very small number of youth all over the region have clandestinely taken to consuming alcohol and non-vegetarian food. Lack of care of the elderly members of the family, on the part of male youth is also regarded as the proof of this indifference. Their preoccupation with television, mobile phones and inter-net is mentioned as additional cause of concern. Not

surprisingly, a large majority of our respondents support the idea of strengthening moral education and training for youngsters through schools, moral educational/spiritual camps, etc.

To sum up, a comparative account of socio-economic change in various aspects of the Jain community of Bundelkhand clearly brings out the uneven nature of social change and development. Thus, economic, educational and occupational aspects have changed relatively much faster than socio-cultural and religious aspects. Needless to say, a few more systematic studies would be required in order to fully understand the course of social change in the Bundelkhand Jain community.

(This article is the summary and conclusion of a research project report on the same topic submitted to the Indian Council of Social Science Research, New Delhi by the author who worked as a Senior Research Fellow of the Council during 2013-15).